

Klein-Gordon Equation and Wave Function in Cosmological Special Theory of Relativity

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Abstract: In the Cosmological Special Theory of Relativity, we study energy-momentum relations, Klein-Gordon equation and wave function.

Keywords: Cosmological special relativity theory; Klein-Gordon equation; Energy-momentum relation

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1. INTRODUCTION

Our article's aim is that we make Klein-Gordon equation and wave function in cosmological special theory of relativity.

At first, space-time relations are in cosmological special theory of relativity (CSTR).[7]

$$ct = \gamma(ct + \frac{v_0}{c}\Omega^2(t_0)x'), \quad x\Omega(t_0) = \gamma(\Omega(t_0)x' + v_0\Omega(t_0)t')$$

$$\begin{aligned} \Omega(t_0)y &= \Omega(t_0)y', \\ \Omega(t_0)z &= \Omega(t_0)z' \end{aligned}, \quad \gamma = 1/\sqrt{1 - \frac{v_0^2}{c^2}\Omega^2(t_0)}, \quad t_0 \text{ is cosmological time} \quad (1)$$

Therefore, proper time is[7]

$$\begin{aligned} d\tau^2 &= dt^2 - \frac{1}{c^2}\Omega^2(t_0)[dx^2 + dy^2 + dz^2] \\ &= dt'^2 - \frac{1}{c^2}\Omega^2(t_0)[dx'^2 + dy'^2 + dz'^2], \quad t_0 \text{ is cosmological time} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Hence, energy-momentum relations are by the fact that energy-momentum are 4-vector in CSTR,

$$\begin{aligned} E &= \gamma(E + v_0\Omega^2(t_0)p_x'), \quad p_x\Omega(t_0) = \gamma(\Omega(t_0)p_x + \frac{v_0}{c^2}\Omega(t_0)E') \\ \Omega(t_0)p_y &= \Omega(t_0)p_y', \\ \Omega(t_0)p_z &= \Omega(t_0)p_z' \end{aligned}, \quad \gamma = 1/\sqrt{1 - \frac{v_0^2}{c^2}\Omega^2(t_0)}, \quad E = m_0c^2 \frac{dt}{d\tau}, \quad \vec{p} = m_0 \frac{d\vec{x}}{d\tau} \quad (3)$$

Therefore, energy-momentum-mass relation is in CSTR,

$$m_0^2c^4 = E^2 - \Omega^2(t_0)p^2c^2 \quad (4)$$

2. KLEIN-GORDON EQUATION AND WAVE FUNCTION IN CSTR

According to [7], matter wave function is in CSTR,

$$\begin{aligned} \phi &= \phi_0 \exp i\Phi = \phi_0 \exp i\left[\frac{\omega t}{\sqrt{\Omega(t_0)}} - \vec{k} \cdot \vec{x} \sqrt{\Omega(t_0)}\right] \\ &= \phi' = \phi_0 \exp i\Phi' = \phi_0 \exp i\left[\frac{\omega' t'}{\sqrt{\Omega(t_0)}} - \vec{k}' \cdot \vec{x}' \sqrt{\Omega(t_0)}\right] \end{aligned}$$

ϕ_0 is amplitude, ω is angular frequency, $k = |\vec{k}|$ is wave number. (5)

If we use Eq(1) in Eq(5), we obtain angular frequency-wave number relation.

$$\begin{aligned} \omega' &= \gamma(\omega - v_0 \Omega(t_0) k_1), \quad k_1' = \gamma(k_1 - \frac{v_0}{c^2} \Omega(t_0) \omega) \\ k_2' &= k_2, k_3' = k_3, \gamma = 1 / \sqrt{1 - \frac{v_0^2}{c^2} \Omega^2(t_0)} \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

In this time, if we define energy-momentum by angular frequency-wave number,

$$E = \hbar \omega, \vec{p} = \frac{\hbar \vec{k}}{\Omega(t_0)} \quad (7)$$

Hence, we obtain the angular frequency-wave number relation about the energy-momentum-mass relation

in CSTR,

$$m_0^2 c^4 = E^2 - \Omega^2(t_0) p^2 c^2 = \hbar^2 \omega^2 - \hbar^2 k^2 c^2 \quad (8)$$

We obtain next result by the transformation of the angular frequency-wave number relation, Eq(6) in CSTR.

$$m_0^2 c^4 = \hbar^2 \omega'^2 - \hbar^2 k'^2 c^2 = \hbar^2 \omega'^2 - \hbar^2 k'^2 c^2 \quad (9)$$

If we define the differential operator about energy-momentum in CSTR,

$$E = i\hbar \sqrt{\Omega(t_0)} \frac{\partial}{\partial t}, \vec{p} = -i\hbar \frac{1}{\Omega(t_0) \sqrt{\Omega(t_0)}} \vec{\nabla} \quad (10)$$

If we apply Eq(10) to Eq(4),

$$m_0^2 c^4 = E^2 - \Omega^2(t_0) p^2 c^2 = \hbar^2 [-\Omega(t_0) (\frac{\partial}{\partial t})^2 + \frac{1}{\Omega(t_0)} c^2 \nabla^2]$$

We finally obtain Klein-Gordon equation in CSTR.

$$\frac{m_0^2 c^2}{\hbar^2} \phi = [-\Omega(t_0) \frac{1}{c^2} (\frac{\partial}{\partial t})^2 + \frac{1}{\Omega(t_0)} \nabla^2] \phi \quad (11)$$

Wave function, Eq(5) satisfy Klein-Gordon equation, Eq(11) in CSTR.

3. CONCLUSION

We are able to describe free particle by Klein-Gordon equation and wave function in CSTR.

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